

SUPPRESSION OF FREE-EDGE DELAMINATION BY HYBRIDIZATION

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Summary

The present study deals with the analytical and experimental investigations carried on toward the suppression of free-edge delamination by reduction of predominant interlaminar stress components. This has been achieved by investigating pure graphite and its hybrids with S-glass for the same stacking sequence.

The material systems used in this study were T300 graphite/1034C epoxy and S-glass/1034C epoxy. Two families of laminates, $(+30_2/90_2)_S$ and $(0_2/+15_2)_S$, were investigated under applied uniaxial tensile and compressive loadings. Location, ply orientations, and volume fractions of the graphite plies and glass plies in hybrid laminates were determined on the basis of stress analysis. It has been demonstrated that for the same laminate orientation and loading condition, the hybrid laminates exhibit reduced out of plane stress components than those for pure graphite laminates. As a result, laminate resistance to delamination is moderately enhanced by hybridization.

Introduction

The presence and growth of free-edge delamination in most cases significantly reduce the load-carrying capability and stiffness of composite laminates. Because of this adverse effect of delamination on the integrity of composite structures, a great deal of work has been reported in the literature. However, most of this work has been concerned with the aspects of stress analysis and prediction of delamination initiation and growth (1-5). A very limited work has been reported on the effort of the controlling aspect of delamination. The delamination can be alleviated by either employing a tough matrix system or change in laminate configuration. A number of different approaches considered in the literature include: 1. a design of a proper stacking sequence of a laminate (6), 2. altering the mechanical properties of certain layers in the region of potential delamination by adding or replacing some layers with toughened materials such as adhesive film, hybridization, etc. (7,8), 3. reinforcing free-edge regions by stitching or wrapping (9,10). To the best of the authors' knowledge, none of these concepts have been subjected to an extensive investigation. A proper combination of the above approaches may eventually lead to complete control of the most feared fracture mode (delamination) in composite laminates.

The main objective of this paper is to investigate the effect of hybridization of laminates on the interlaminar stress distribution in the critical region and initiation of delamination gearing toward the suppression of free-edge delamination. This has been achieved by studying the response characteristics of laminates of pure graphite and hybrid of graphite and S-glass with the same orientations. Two types of laminates which exhibit delamination under axial load due to either interlaminar normal stress or shear stress were chosen. The location, the ply orientation, and volume fraction of S-glass plies in hybrid laminates were determined on the basis of stress analysis done by the global-local model developed by Pagano and Soni (3). The results of stress analysis in conjunction with the average stress failure criterion are used to predict the location (interface) and threshold stress of the free-edge delamination. The predictions are compared with the experimental observation under in-plane uniaxial tensile and compressive loading conditions.

The effect of proper layup in hybrid laminates for reducing the out of plane stress levels has been demonstrated. The results indicate that the laminate resistance to delamination can be enhanced by using hybrid laminates without a marked loss in stiffness and strength of the laminate due to hybridization.

Analytical Background

Figure 1 shows the laminate geometry and stress components in the free-edge region of a multidirectional composite laminate under applied in-plane tension. In this laminate, the out of plane stress components (σ_z , τ_{xz} , and τ_{yz}) are mainly responsible for initiation and growth of free-edge delamination. The nature and magnitude of interlaminar stress components vary widely depending upon the laminate orientation, stacking sequence, and material properties. The stress analysis was conducted and the results are given for all the laminates. The results are presented in graphical form showing the stress levels over a distance equal to half of the laminate thickness in the y-direction at each interface. Prediction of delamination threshold stress was made using the approach developed in Ref (11,12). This approach assumes delamination to occur when the average value of any of the out of plane stress components, σ_z , τ_{xz} , τ_{yz} over a

Figure 1 - Laminate geometry and interlaminar stress components.

fixed distance, in this case one ply thickness from the free-edge in the y-direction, reaches its relevant strength of the material system. Interlaminar tensile and shear strength of the material systems are considered to be the same as the in-plane strength values of the material systems. The following are the material properties utilized for the stress analysis and the prediction of onset of delamination for laminates used in this study:

	Graphite/Epoxy	S-glass/Epoxy
<u>Elastic properties</u>		
$E_L, 10^6 \text{ psi}$	20.01	7.3
$E_T, 10^6 \text{ psi}$	1.45	2.71
$G_{LT}, 10^6 \text{ psi}$	0.8	1.0
$G_{TT}, 10^6 \text{ psi}$	0.6	0.7
ν_{LT}	0.3	0.28
ν_{TT}	0.6	0.56
<u>Strength, 10^3 ksi</u>		
X_L	216.10	256.27
X'_L	216.10	145.03
X_T	9.40	9.57
X'_T	29.01	37.13
$X_S = X'_S$	12.47	15.5

where E, G, and ν stand for Young's modulus, shear modulus, and Poisson's ratio, respectively. L is the fiber direction and T the transverse direction. In strength the prime denotes compressive strength or negative shear strength.

Experiment

The material systems used in this work are T300 graphite/1034C epoxy and S-glass/1034C epoxy supplied in prepreg form by Fiberite Corporation. The following pure and hybrid laminates were considered:

pure graphite	$(+30_2c/90_2c)_S$	$(0_2c/\pm 15_2c)_S$
Hybrid I	$(+30_2c/90_2s)_S$	$(0_2c/\pm 15_2s)_S$
Hybrid II	$(+30_2s/90_2c)_S$	$(0_2s/\pm 15_2c)_S$

where c and s denote graphite and S-glass, respectively.

Panels of the above pure and hybrid laminates were fabricated in an autoclave according to the manufacturer's recommended cure cycle. In addition, unidirectional and $(+45)_S$ laminates of the pure graphite and the pure S-glass were fabricated to generate the elastic properties and strength. The fiber volume content was determined to be approximately 67 percent in both graphite and S-glass laminates. Straight-sided specimens were cut from the panels using a diamond impregnated saw. All specimens were 6" long (4" in gage length) and 3/4" wide. In order to facilitate microscopic examination, the free edges of the specimens were ground with sandpaper and then polished with one micron polishing powder. Three specimens in each laminate were instrumented with an axial and a transverse strain gage to determine elastic constants.

All specimens were tested on an MTS testing machine with a constant crosshead movement corresponding to the strain rate of approximately 0.005 in/in-min. In compression test a pair of side support devices was employed to prevent buckling of the specimen. The strain level at the onset of delamination was determined by acoustic emission technique. For that purpose, an acoustic emission transducer was mounted on the surface of the specimen using an elastic rubber band with high vacuum grease to improve coupling. As soon as the moment of delamination was indicated by acoustic events, the specimen was unloaded. The polished free-edges of the specimen were then subjected to microscopic examination for insuring the delamination and determining its location in interfaces. In order to identify the dominant failure mode, the fracture surface of delamination was examined using a scanning electron microscope (SEM). The SEM sample (0.3" x 0.4") was prepared from the specimen with a considerable growth of delamination prior to final failure.

Results and Discussion

The interlaminar stress distributions computed on the basis of the Global-local model (3) at different interfaces of the laminate are given in Figures 2 and 3 for pure graphite laminates of $(+30_2c/90_2c)_S$ and $(0_2c/\pm 15_2c)_S$, respectively. The interlaminar stresses are plotted along the y-direction (width) from the free edge to the point corresponding to half the laminate thickness for a unit applied strain in the axial direction. In both laminates σ_z is the only nonzero interlaminar stress component at the midplane, whereas at the other interfaces all three components (σ_z , τ_{xz} and τ_{yz}) are nonzero. In all the cases except for σ_z

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 2 - Interlaminar stress distribution for the $(+30_2c/90_2c)_s$ laminate, arrowhead indicates the interface considered.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 3 - Interlaminar stresses distribution for the $(0_2c/+15_2c)_S$ laminate, arrowhead indicates the interface considered.

at the midplane of the $(0_2c/+15_2c)_S$ laminate, there exists a large gradient of predominant stress component along the y-direction in the vicinity of the free-edge region. The maximum value is at or very near the free edge.

Figures 4 and 5 show the predominant interlaminar stress components showing the effect of hybridization on the stress level at the interface in the free-edge region. In the cases considered here, the hybrid composite has smaller interlaminar stress than in the pure graphite laminate. Figure 4 shows a comparison of the predominant interlaminar stress components at each interface of pure graphite and hybrid in $(+30_2/90_2)_S$ laminates. The σ_z is predominant in both the midplane as well as the 90/-30 interface whereas τ_{xz} is predominant at the 30/-30 interface as shown in Figure 4. In the family of $(0_2/+15_2)_S$ laminates, σ_z is predominant at the midplane and τ_{xz} is predominant at the 15/-15 and -15/0 interfaces. Since σ_z is not large enough to cause delamination for this laminate, delamination may occur due to τ_{xz} at the 15/-15 interface (Fig 5b). It should be noted that the sign of shear stress is immaterial for the failure of the specimen. Thus this laminate will delaminate under both tensile and compressive load.

A summary of predicted and experimental values is shown in Table I. In analytical predictions the aforementioned strength values are used. In $(+30_2/90_2)_S$ laminates the prediction of onset of delamination is very close to the experiment, and the difference is less than 11 percent. Under uniaxial tensile load delamination is due to tensile σ_z at the midplane. However, under uniaxial compression, delamination occurs at the interface of the 30/-30 due to τ_{xz} . The interlaminar stress distribution shown in Figs 2 to 5 changes its sign when the applied load is compression instead of tension. Because the compressive strength is approximately four times greater than tensile strength in the transverse direction of this material system, the compressive σ_z at the midplane under applied compression is not high enough to cause delamination. In other words the ratio of compressive transverse strength and compressive σ_z is greater than the ratio of shear strength and τ_{xz} .

In $(0_2/+15_2)_S$ laminates, the σ_z is too small to cause delamination whereas τ_{xz} is predominant at the 15/-15 interface. The specimen has failed before the σ_z reaches its transverse tensile strength, and consequently the delamination is due to τ_{xz} at the interface of the 15/-15 layer. Since the sign of shear stress is immaterial in failure of this material system, delamination would occur in applied uniaxial tension and compression at the same interface. There is a considerable difference between the prediction and the experimental values of the delamination threshold stress level in the family of the $(0_2/+15_2)_S$ laminate. One of the main reasons for this difference is considered to be the interaction of σ_z and τ_{xz} . Under the combined state of stress at the interface, the composite shear strength either decreases or increases depending upon the sign of axial stress.

Hybrid laminates in all cases show some degree of improvement in threshold strain level for onset of delamination in both analysis and experiment as shown in Table I. However, in terms of stress the delamination threshold stress level in some hybrid laminates is smaller than that of pure graphite because of reduced effective stiffness in the axial direction.

Figures 6 to 9 show some typical microphotographs of delamination observed in this study. In all the cases except for the family of the $(+30_2/90_2)_S$ laminate under tensile loading, delamination occurred at the interface predicted as listed in Table I, and no transverse crack was observed prior to delamination. However, in the family of the $(+30_2/90_2)_S$

Figure 4 - Comparison of the predominant interlaminar stress components for the family of $[\pm 30_2/90_2]_s$ laminates.

Figure 5 - Comparison of the predominant interlaminar stress components for the family of $(0_2/+15_2)_s$ laminates.

Table I. Analytical and Experimental Results on Onset of Delamination

Laminate	Type of loading	Avg stress components, ksi for $\epsilon_x = 0.1\%$			ϵ_x at onset of delamination, %		Observed interface delaminated
		σ_z	τ_{xz}	Interface	Prediction	Experiment	
Pure graphite [+30 ₂ c/90 ₂ c] _s	Tension compression	2.3 ≈0	0 3.0	Midplane +30/-30	0.33 0.42	0.37 0.45	Midplane & -30/90 30/-30
Hybrid I [+30 ₂ c/90 ₂ s] _s	Tension compression	1.88 ≈0	0 2.80	Midplane +30/-30	0.51 0.45	0.46 0.50	Midplane & -30/90 30/-30
Hybrid II [+30 ₂ s/90 ₂ c] _s	Tension compression	0.88 ≈0	0 1.32	Midplane +30/-30	0.85 1.18	0.76 1.26	Midplane & -30/90 30/-30
Pure graphite [0 ₂ /+15 ₂] _s	Compression	0.08	4.00	+15/-15	0.31	0.45	15/-15
Hybrid I [0 ₂ c/+15 ₂ s] _s	Tension compression	-0.03 0.03	1.18 1.18	+15/-15 +15/-15	1.31 1.31	1.38 1.14	15/-15 15/-15
Hybrid II [0 ₂ s/+15 ₂ c] _s	Tension compression	-0.28 0.28	3.4 3.4	+15/-15 +15/-15	0.37 0.37	0.67 0.50	15/-15 & 0/15 15/-15

(a) tension

(b) compression

Figure 6 - Microphotographs showing delamination in the $(+30_2c/90_2c)_s$ laminate.

(a) tension

(b) compression

Figure 7 - Microphotographs showing delamination in the $(+30_2c/90_2s)_s$ laminate.

(a) tension

(b) compression

Figure 8 - Microphotographs showing delamination in the $(0_2c/+15_2c)_s$ laminate.

(a) tension

(b) compression

Figure 9 - Microphotographs showing delamination in the $(0_2s/+15_2c)_s$ laminate.

laminate under tensile loading, delamination followed the multiple transverse cracks in the 90-deg layer. Some of these cracks were extended to the adjacent -45-deg layer and then turned into axial direction at the -45/45 interface as shown in Figures 6a and 7a. In these laminates, delamination was observed at the -45/90 interface as well as at the midplane as shown in Figures 6a and 7a. In other words the delamination path wandered from the midplane to the adjacent -45/90 interface. This appears to be mainly attributed to a combination of transverse cracks and presence of the relatively high σ_z at the -45/90 interface as shown in Figures 2a and 4a.

In order to identify the fracture modes implied in the analysis, the fracture surface of selected specimens which delaminate due to tensile σ_z and τ_{xz} were examined using a scanning electron microscope. Figures 10 to 13 present SEM photographs of some typical specimens examined. Figures 10 and 11 show the fracture surface of the midplane and -30/90 interface, respectively, in the $(+30_2s/90_2c)_s$ laminate under tension. The matrix cleavage and lack of laceration at the midplane in Figure 10 are indicative of fracture created mainly by tensile normal stress. A few fiber breaks are considered to have been caused by tearing during the separation of the delaminated surface. The fracture surface of the -30/90 interface in Figure 11 shows laceration and matrix cleavage caused by a combination of tensile and shear stress. Figures 12 and 13 show the fracture surface of the 30/-30 interface in pure graphite and hybrid laminate under compression. The extensive laceration is mainly created by interlaminar shear as predicted by analysis. There is hardly any fiber breakage in the fracture surface due to τ_{xz} in the sample examined. All the SEM observations appear to support the analytical results on the failure mode.

Midplane

Figure 10 - SEM photograph showing delamination fracture at midplane of the $(+30_2s/90_2c)_s$ laminate under applied tension.

-30/90 Interface

Figure 11 - SEM photograph showing delamination fracture at the -30/90 interface of the $(+30_2s/90c)_s$ laminate under applied tension.

+30/-30 Interface

Figure 12 - SEM photographs showing delamination fracture at the +30/-30 interface of $(+30_2s/90_2c)$ laminate under applied compression.

Figure 13 - SEM photographs showing delamination fracture at the +30/-30 interface of (+30 s/90 c) laminate under applied compression.

Conclusion

Analytical and experimental study on the free-edge delamination for pure graphite and its hybrid with S-glass was carried out for suppressing the delamination in layered composites. In the laminates considered here, the hybridization of pure graphite/epoxy has reduced the interlaminar stress values. The amount of reduction in the predominant interlaminar stress values varies widely depending upon the type of laminate including the orientation and the location of the S-glass layers. As a result, laminate resistance to delamination is moderately enhanced by hybridization.

The predicted onset of delamination loads or strains on the basis of average stress failure theory are in most cases close to the experimental values. The distinct modes of onset of delamination, either due to τ_{xz} or σ_z , have been pointed out by SEM pictures. It has been found that SEM provides a very useful way of identifying the modes of delamination failure of composite laminates.

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